

CLINICAL AND EPIDEMIOLOGICAL FEATURES OF VIRAL HEPATITIS A IN CHILDREN

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Abstract. *Viral hepatitis A (HAV) is the most common liver disease, accounting for 65-75% of all viral hepatitis. Despite the fact, that susceptibility to viral hepatitis A is universal, the disease is most often registered in children over 1 year of age (especially aged 3-12 years in organized groups) and in young people (20-29 years). The article presents the clinical and epidemiological features of HAV in children. In the hospital of infectious diseases, cases of HAV were more often (614 - 51.5%) registered in school-age children than in children aged 1 to 5 years (285 - 23.9%). Clinically, it manifested itself as an acute onset of the disease in the form of influenza-like and dyspeptic variants and a pronounced intoxication syndrome; most often (58.3%) it occurred in severe and moderate (41.7%) forms of the disease. In order to expand the coverage of immunization of the entire population and its accessibility against HAV, it is necessary to introduce it into the "National Calendar of Preventive Vaccinations of the Republic of Uzbekistan," which will play an important role in reducing the incidence of viral hepatitis "A" among children.*

Keywords: *epidemiology, clinic, hepatitis A virus, children.*

Relevance. Viral hepatitis A (HAV) is the most common liver disease, accounting for 65-75% of all viral hepatitis. Despite the fact, that susceptibility to viral hepatitis A is universal, the disease is most often registered in children over 1 year of age (especially aged 3-12 years in organized groups) and in young people (20-29 years). The susceptibility of children under 1 year of age to viral hepatitis A is low due to the retention of passive immunity transmitted from the mother. Viral hepatitis A (HAV) is an acute infectious disease caused by an RNA-containing virus, belongs to the Picornaviridae family, Hepatovirus genus, with a fecal-oral mechanism of infection and is characterized by acute onset, short-term symptoms of intoxication, rapidly transient liver dysfunction, cyclical and benign course, with a favorable outcome [1- 5]. The aim of the study was to investigate the clinical and epidemiological features of viral hepatitis in children during the seasonal epidemic rise.

Materials and methods of the study. The diagnosis of HAV was made on the basis of epidemiological investigations, clinical data with changes in biochemical parameters, as well as the determination of antibodies to HAV (anti-HAV IgM) by the enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) in patients hospitalized in the department of infectious diseases of the Republican Scientific and Practical Center for Epidemiology and Microbiology of the Republic of Uzbekistan. A statistical retrospective epidemiological analysis of data on the incidence of hepatitis A among the population of the Republic of Uzbekistan as a whole was carried out.

Study results. In 2023, a seasonal epidemic increase in HAV was registered in the Republic of Uzbekistan (66994 cases) than for the same period in 2022 (29660 cases), and the largest increase in the number of sick children with HAV was registered in the detection season starting from September. In addition, it was also established that in 2023, out of the total number of cases

in the Republic, 52502 children under the age of 14 were registered, and in 2022, only 26,994 children under the age of 14 were registered, which is 25508 more cases.

Dynamics of incidence of hepatitis A in the context of administrative territories in the Republic of Uzbekistan for the period 2022-2023.

Of the 1191 children with HAV hospitalized in January-December 2023 in the department of infectious diseases of the RSNPMCEMPZ of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the disease was registered in 614 (51.5%) school-age children from 5 to 14 years old, compared to 285 (23.9%) children aged 1 to 5 years.

Dynamics of HAV incidence by administrative territories in the Republic of Uzbekistan for the period 2022-2023

Under our observation were 72 (11.7%) sick children who were on inpatient treatment. From the medical history of all children with HAV, it was established that the incubation period lasted from 15 to 45 days, and the duration of the prodromal (prejaundice) period was 4-8 days (on average 5-7 days) and was characterized in the majority of 65 (90.3%) by an acute onset and a pronounced syndrome intoxication, with an increase in body temperature to 38–40 °C for 1-3 days, and children complained of headache 58 (80.5%), decreased appetite 54 (75%), bitter taste in the mouth and bad breath 36 (50%), nausea 35 (48.6%), feeling of heaviness in the epigastric region 32 (44.4%), pain in the right hypochondrium 25 (34.7%). In addition, in the majority of children, 42 (58.3%) were found to have characteristic irritability and increased nervousness, in

39 (54.2%) capriciousness and loss of interest in games, in 26 (36.1%) sleep disorders in the form of sleep inversion and in 25 (34.7%) repeated vomiting was noted, in 12 (16.7%) children repeated vomiting. Also, 15 (20.8%) children with HAV had flatulence, 19 (26.4%) children had constipation. By the end of the pre-jaundice period, all children had urine with the color of dark beer, most of 53 (73.6%) children had mushy acholian stools. The duration of the peak period in all children with HAV was an average of 2-3 weeks. It should be noted that jaundice in children with HAV appeared suddenly, within 1–2 days "overnight" and with the appearance of jaundice syndrome in most 69 (95.8%) children there was an improvement in general well-being and was established by a decrease in complaints associated with the normalization of body temperature to normal or low-grade levels, a decrease in headache and other intoxicating manifestations, which serves as an important differential diagnostic sign of HAV. It was revealed that jaundice staining in the majority of 70 (97.2%) children appeared at the beginning of the period on the oral mucosa (frenulum of the tongue, hard palate), later on the sclera, on the skin and increased rapidly, usually reaching a maximum in 3-5 days, in the next 5-10 days it remained at the same level, and then the intensity of jaundice decreased after 2-3 days and disappeared after 7-10 days. In addition, in the jaundice period, almost all children had asthenic syndrome and enlargement of the liver, and in 55 (76.4%) children, palpation revealed painful, 11 (15.2%) children had an enlargement of the spleen, 45 (62.5%) children had moderate bradycardia and a decrease in blood pressure, 35 (48.6%) had deafness of heart sounds, and 23 (31.9%) children had problems in a tongue.

In further studies, we analyzed the biochemical parameters in children with HAV. Such indicators as total protein and its fractions, hepatic-specific enzymes ALT, AST (alanine amino- and aspartate aminotransferases), bilirubin and its fractions, as well as protein-sedimentary samples were analyzed. Thus, during the biochemical examination of the blood from the onset of the disease, all children with HAV reveal an increase in ALT and AST activity by 4 or more times from the standard data, and the activity of ALT prevails over the activity of AST by two or more times, which is an early and reliable indicator of damage to hepatocytes, an increase in the amount of urobilin in the urine was noted, and at the end of the pre-jaundice period bile pigments are found. In the jaundice period, an increase in total bilirubin was observed in the blood of all children, and in 42 (58.3%) in the range of 85-190 $\mu\text{mol g/l}$ and the advantage was due to an increase in the level of bound bilirubin, alkaline phosphatase activity above 105 U/l, as well as a decrease (disappearance) of urobilin bodies in the urine. Treatment of children with HAV was carried out in accordance with the approved clinical protocols (Order No542 dated August 27, 2018 "On further improvement of measures for the diagnosis, treatment and prevention of viral hepatitis in the Republic of Uzbekistan").

The prevalence of hepatitis A can be reduced through non-specific prophylaxis, such as improved sanitation, food safety, adequate supply of safe drinking water, proper disposal of wastewater in communities, and good personal hygiene, such as regular hand washing before meals and after using the toilet. In the Republic of Uzbekistan from 2021, vaccination against hepatitis A is carried out according to epidemiological indications. The population immunization program against infectious diseases has always been and continues to be one of the main public health priorities in Uzbekistan and part of the state's comprehensive concern for the health of citizens, especially children. An important achievement of the country over the years is the high political commitment to the immunization program, as demonstrated by high immunization coverage rates and the implementation of ongoing cost-sharing commitments for routine vaccines

[6]. But the most effective means of combating hepatitis A is routine immunization of children, i.e. it is necessary to adjust the method of specific prevention and introduce it into the "National Calendar of Preventive Vaccinations", thereby expanding immunization coverage and accessibility to the entire population, which will play an important role in reducing the incidence of viral hepatitis A among organized children.

Conclusions. Thus, during the epidemic outbreak of the disease, HAV in the hospital of infectious diseases at the RSNPMCEMPZ was registered more often (51.5%) in school-age children than in children aged 1 to 5 years (23.9%). Clinically, it manifested itself as an acute onset of the disease according to the influenza-like and dyspeptic variants and a pronounced intoxication syndrome, most often it occurred in severe (58.3%) and moderate (41.7%) forms of the disease. According to the results of the analysis of statistical data, taking into account the unfavorable epidemiological situation for the detection of HAV in the republic, in order to expand the coverage of immunization of the entire population and accessibility, it is necessary to adjust the prevention method and introduce it into the "National Calendar of Preventive Vaccinations", which will play an important role in reducing the incidence of viral hepatitis "A" among organized children.

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